

1

saqulek

2

Teng' uq.

3

Mit' llraa.

4

kum' agyak

5

qalnga' aq

6

aqllaq

2

It is flying.

1

bird

4

eagle

3

It has landed.

6

wind

5

raven

7

teng'usta

8

Tangrru.

9

Pektut.

10

cawiguanguasa'aq

8

**See it. /Look
at it. /Spot it.**

7

pilot

10

**Drone (an unmanned aerial
vehicle)**

9

They are working.